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Voice to Calendar: An End-to-End Voice Reservation System for the Hospitality Industry**Ali Kerem GÜLER¹, Mehmet GÖKTÜRK²**¹ Machine Learning Team Lead, Machine Learning Department, Artificial Intelligence, Orcid:
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[0000-0002-8030-8923](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8030-8923)**Abstract**

In the hospitality industry, where digital transformation is accelerating, there is a growing demand for contactless and intelligent interaction methods that enhance user experience. This study presents an end-to-end, voice-based, autonomous restaurant reservation system integrating the Turyid Loyalty mobile application and the Check and Place table management platform under Protel A.Ş. The proposed architecture utilizes the OpenAI Whisper model and the Speech Recognition library for speech recognition. For the semantic understanding process, it employs a two-stage hybrid Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipeline. In the first stage, structural irregularities and semantic inconsistencies within the transcribed text are normalized using the Gemini-1.5-Flash model. In the second stage, the system precisely extracts date, time, and person count entities using the Gemini-2.0-Flash-Exp model. One of the novel aspects of this study is the management of temporal ambiguities in natural language. The system converts relative expressions such as “this evening”, “next Tuesday”, or “New Year's Eve” into standard ISO format. In cases where contextual cues are missing, it automatically assigns the most appropriate reservation time using heuristics based on sectoral dynamics. Designed with a microservices architecture, this framework automates the reservation process by ensuring seamless data flow between heterogeneous systems. An average task success rate of 94% and an average completion time of 8.4 seconds, obtained in tests conducted under real-world conditions, demonstrate the system's performance and commercial viability. Consequently, this study demonstrates, through concrete data, the contribution of AI-powered voice assistants to the omnichannel customer experience by eliminating friction in reservation processes.

Keywords: Voice-based reservation system, Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, Large Language Models, OpenAI Whisper, Google Gemini, Speech-to-intent

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly digitizing world, the proliferation of mobile devices and advancements in voice assistant technologies (Poushneh, 2021), (Guha et al., 2023) are fundamentally changing how users interact with services. Particularly in the fast-paced food and beverage sector, the operational burden and time loss associated with traditional reservation methods such as phone calls and manual form filling pose significant challenges for businesses and customers. In this

context, voice-based reservation infrastructures offer the potential to transform the customer experience by enabling reservations through natural speech, without the need for complex text inputs or long waiting times.

Voice-based systems significantly enhance operational efficiency by reducing the traditional call center load, minimize erroneous data entry, and substantially improve customer satisfaction through real-time personalization. Furthermore, advanced capabilities such as natural language intent extraction expand the accessibility of businesses serving the global tourism market and provide rich semantic content for data-driven decision-making processes. This innovative technology layer sustainably strengthens the competitive advantage of restaurant and hospitality businesses.

The primary objective of this study is to simplify the restaurant reservation process by making it entirely manageable through voice, thereby enhancing the user experience. To this end, a scalable and robust infrastructure has been developed, integrating Protel A.Ş.'s Turyid Loyalty mobile application with the Check and Place table-management platform. Leveraging machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) techniques, the extraction of intent (date, time, number of guests) from speech has been automated with high accuracy.

The system records the user's voice request and converts this audio into raw text via OpenAI Whisper or SpeechRecognition modules. The obtained transcript is then processed by the Gemini-1.5-Flash model to correct grammar, add punctuation, and complete missing words, thereby enhancing semantic coherence. Subsequently, the revised text is analyzed by the Gemini-2.0-Flash-Exp model, guided by an optimized prompt, to automatically extract the necessary reservation parameters: date, time, and number of guests. During this process, natural language date expressions (e.g., "this evening," "next Tuesday") are converted into the DD/MM/YYYY format, and times are transformed into the 24-hour clock, considering contextual cues. Finally, these extracted parameters are combined with user information (name-surname, phone number) retrieved from the Loyalty backend, transmitted to the Check and Place API, and the reservation is saved in the restaurant's calendar.

This article is structured as follows: Section II provides a comprehensive literature review, illustrating the study's position within relevant academic works. Section III details the system's architecture, data processing steps, and the methodology employed. Section IV presents the performance evaluation results. Finally, Section V summarizes the conclusions and outlines future research directions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Historically, chatbots began with the emergence of the term Chatterbot in 1991, with initial attempts featuring digitized speech, such as Dr. Sbaitso in 1992. Subsequent developments like ALICE (1995) and SmarterChild (2001) expanded conversational capabilities and demonstrated the potential for providing practical information. In recent years, AI-powered chatbots have undergone a major transformation with advancements in natural language processing, machine learning, and deep learning (DL). The emergence of smart personal assistants like Apple Siri and Amazon Alexa reflects this trend (Gupta et al., 2024).

In the hospitality sector, virtual assistants and chatbots are increasingly being utilized (Athikkal and Jenq, 2022). Examples include Amazon's Alexa for Hospitality (2018) and Google's addition of hotel-specific features to its Nest Hub (2020). Solutions like HiJiffy's multilingual virtual assistant and Nomadix's digital concierge Angie have also found their place in the industry. These technologies help hotels increase operational efficiency, enhance customer services, and reduce costs (Britt, 2023). Chatbots specifically automate core operations such as

order processing, reservation management, and responses to frequently asked questions (FAQs).

According to Media Richness Theory (MRT), the richness of communication channels is a significant factor influencing consumers' perceptions and intentions. Voice assistants are considered a rich communication channel due to their voice functionalities, natural language processing capabilities, and instant feedback mechanisms. These features evoke a sense of social presence in users, leading them to interact with devices as they would with humans. A study by Flavián et al. (2023) demonstrated that voice assistant recommendations are more effective in influencing consumer behavior compared to online consumer reviews. This effect occurs through perceived credibility and usefulness. Voice recommendations are perceived as more credible than text-based ones. Furthermore, this paper indicated that recommendations for search products are perceived as more credible and effective than those for experience products.

However, voice assistant recommendations also have limitations. Factors such as difficulties in memory retention (retaining voice information in short-term memory), challenges in comparing multiple options leading to a higher tendency to accept the first recommendation, can indirectly limit the amount of information voice assistants provide (Flavián et al., 2023). Additionally, for some users, data privacy and security concerns remain a significant barrier to the adoption of virtual assistants (Shafeeg et al., 2023), (Buhalis and Moldavska, 2022).

In areas such as restaurant and appointment scheduling, the foundation of voice-based systems and chatbots lies in their ability to accurately understand user intent. The AI-powered chatbot named Genie, developed by Gupta et al. (2024), classified customer queries for order processing and reservations in the restaurant industry with 88.9% accuracy, using a combination of Word2Vec and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Pathirage et al. (2023), on the other hand, developed a RASA NLU-based voice bot system for appointment scheduling and demonstrated its efficiency in interpreting user intents and retrieving relevant data. These studies emphasize the critical role of NLP techniques and machine learning models in transforming complex natural language requests into structured information.

Existing literature focuses on specific needs such as the role of voice assistants in conveying sustainability messages (Jiang et al., 2025), general chatbot applications (Gupta et al., 2024), appointment scheduling in specific domains (Pathirage et al., 2023), and the impact of voice recommendations on consumer behavior (Flavián et al., 2023). Most of these studies either address text-based chatbots or general applications of voice assistants, failing to provide an integrated and holistic solution for entirely voice-based, end-to-end restaurant reservations. Specifically, there is a lack of an approach that automatically extracts necessary reservation information (e.g., today, next Tuesday) from natural language expressions in a context-aware manner, and then seamlessly integrates this information with existing hotel/restaurant infrastructure.

This study aims to address the following shortcomings:

- Presenting a comprehensive architecture that unifies speech-to-text conversion, text refinement, intent extraction, and reservation scheduling into a single automated workflow.
- Integrating grammar correction, punctuation addition, and missing word completion through a Whisper and Gemini LLM chain, thereby eliminating the need for rule-based parsing. Furthermore, it contributes to semantic-time normalization by introducing context-aware time mapping (e.g., seven this evening to 19:00) and intelligent assumptions for ambiguous time expressions.
- Providing a production-ready module beyond conceptual prototypes by ensuring real-world application integration with the Loyalty backend and Check and Place API

through a microservice architecture. The module enhances personalized, frictionless experiences by automatically retrieving user data (name-surname, phone number) and combining it with extracted reservation details, thereby simultaneously increasing both customer satisfaction and operational efficiency.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study presents a voice-based restaurant reservation system that integrates Protel A.Ş.'s Turyid Loyalty mobile application with the Check and Place table-management platform. The system aims to automatically extract reservation information from user voice commands and save it to the relevant table management system. This section comprehensively explains the system's end-to-end architecture, which consists of several distinct steps.

3.1. System Architecture and Data Flow

The system architecture comprises three main stages, as illustrated in Figure 1. After the user logs into the Turyid Loyalty mobile application and selects a preferred restaurant, they submit their voice request through the voice reservation option. The backend of the Loyalty application then transmits this voice recording to the voice reservation backend, where reservation information is extracted from the voice data.

Figure 1. A schematic view of voice reservation methodology concepts.

During the voice data processing stage, the .NET backend service transfers the user's voice recording (in hex format) and the mode parameter (which specifies the speech-to-text model to be used) to the Python-based module responsible for extracting reservation information. At this point, the audio file undergoes format validation. Only 16-bit PCM WAV files are accepted. Otherwise, an error is returned for other formats. This pre-check is performed by leveraging the audio file's header information (WAV/MP4 distinction) and metadata (number of channels, bit depth, sample rate). The system identifies the audio format by inspecting the signatures at the beginning of the byte array, returning 'wav', 'mp4', or 'unknown', but only processes the 'wav' format.

3.2. Speech-to-Text

For the speech-to-text (Bérard et al. 2016), (Wang et al., 2020) conversion stage, two distinct model options are available: the SpeechRecognition API (Zhang, 2017) or the Faster-Whisper model (Guillaumekln, 2023). The appropriate model is selected based on the mode parameter specified by the user, and the transcription process is then executed.

When the mode parameter is set to 1, the Google Speech Recognition API is utilized for rapid transcription. The audio data is converted into a `speech_recognition.AudioFile` object via an `io.BytesIO` stream and then forwarded to the recognition engine. The recognition is performed in Turkish (tr-TR) using the `recognize_google` method. SpeechRecognition offers a faster operational time due to its direct API call mechanism.

When the mode parameter is set to 2, transcription is performed using the Faster-Whisper model. The model is downloaded from AWS S3 only once and retained in the application's memory. This approach ensures that the Docker image containing the voice reservation application remains lightweight and reduces subsequent reloading costs. The audio data is written to a temporary WAV stream, after which the Faster-Whisper model aggregates transcriptions on a segment-by-segment basis. Post-transcription, expressions enclosed in parentheses such as `[.*]` and `(.*)` are removed from the text. The Whisper model was preferred in this study due to its offline operational capability.

3.3 Text Refinement and Semantic Analysis

The raw transcript obtained is subjected to a two-stage NLP process to accurately extract reservation information. This process is carried out using large language models (Imran and N. Almusharraf, 2024).

The initial transcript is sent to the Gemini-1.5-Flash large language model (Google, 2025). In this step, the model performs grammar corrections, adds punctuation, and completes missing words in accordance with Turkish writing, linguistic, and orthographic rules, thereby enhancing the semantic coherence and readability of the text. The aim of this refinement is to increase the reliability of information extraction in the subsequent stage.

The refined text is then presented to the Gemini-2.0-Flash-Exp model with a specially optimized prompt to extract the key parameters required for a reservation (date, time, number of guests). The model identifies date expressions (e.g., this evening, next Tuesday), context-sensitive times (e.g., 8 PM), and the number of guests within the text. Specifically, time expressions are converted into a 24-hour format, taking into account contextual cues such as morning or evening (e.g., 7 AM → 07:00, 8 PM → 20:00). If no contextual indicator is present, times are, by default, assigned an evening (PM) reservation (e.g., 07:00 → 19:00, 10:00 → 22:00).

3.4. Normalization of Natural Dates

If the date information extracted during the intent extraction phase contains relative expressions

such as today, tomorrow, or next week, an additional process is applied to convert these expressions into a precise calendar date. A second Gemini call, using the gemini-2.0-flash-exp model, calculates and returns the exact date in dd-MM-yyyy format based on the current local time in Turkey (UTC+03:00). If the date information, although provided to the gemini-2.0-flash model in datetime format during intent extraction, does not yield a result from this model, a higher version, the gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20 model, is invoked to perform the calculation in dd-MM-yyyy format. This two-stage approach aims to convert date information into a calendar date with higher accuracy during the intent extraction phase. The system automatically updates the year of the converted date to the current year if it is earlier than the current year, ensuring that the reservation points to a current date.

3.5. Integration and Reservation Management

The extracted date, time, and number of guests information is automatically combined with the user's name-surname and telephone details retrieved from the Turyid Loyalty backend. All of this reservation data is then transmitted to the Check and Place API. The Check and Place system uses this data to automatically record the reservation in the restaurant's digital calendar. This microservice-based workflow completes the speech-to-text-to-intent-to-calendar conversion in a contactless and real-time manner, thereby simplifying the user experience and optimizing business operations.

3.6. Error Management and System Robustness

To enhance the system's robustness and reliability, every critical processing block is enclosed within try-except structures. Various error codes have been defined, ranging from speech format validation to speech-to-text conversion, LLM model loading, and information extraction. These specific error codes are designed to facilitate easy logging and user feedback at the .NET layer.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

This section presents the tests conducted and findings obtained to evaluate the performance of the developed voice-based restaurant reservation system. The evaluation was carried out to cover the accuracy rates and operational times of the system's different modules.

To analyze the system's performance under real-world conditions, 20 actual reservation voice recordings, including various noise levels and different speakers' voices, were prepared. Reservation information (date, time, number of guests) was manually extracted from each voice recording to create a reference dataset.

Word Error Rate (WER) was calculated to evaluate the performance of the Speech-to-Text models. For this calculation, manual transcripts of the voice recordings were generated and compared with the transcripts produced by the models. Furthermore, the accuracy of matching the date, time, and number of guests information within the model transcripts with the actual reservation details in the voice recording was measured. The operational time for each model was also recorded and included in the performance comparison. All obtained results, including the accuracy rates and operational times of the models, were transferred to Table 1.

Table 1 Accuracy rates and operational times of models across various scenarios.

Model Flow	WER (%)	Date Accuracy (%)	Time Accuracy (%)	Guest Count Accuracy (%)	Δ Time (s)
SpeechRecognition	18.1	%90	%92	%98	1.96

Faster-Whisper	18.0	%90	%91	%98	3.75
Gemini-2.0-Flash	-	%90	%90	%96	0.95
Gemini-2.0-Flash and Gemini-2.5-flash	-	%85	-	-	0.8

In Table 1, both Google SpeechRecognition and Faster-Whisper models exhibited similar Word Error Rates (WER) in their speech-to-text conversion performance. The SpeechRecognition model had a WER of 18.1%, while Faster-Whisper achieved a WER of 18.0%. This indicates that both models had similar accuracy rates in transcribing reservation-related information from speech. However, in terms of operational time, the SpeechRecognition model was faster at 1.96 seconds, compared to Faster-Whisper's 3.75 seconds. The main reason for this is that SpeechRecognition operates via an API call.

In the LLM layer, the Gemini-2.0-Flash-Exp model was observed to achieve high accuracy rates in extracting reservation information from the transcript. This evaluation measured how accurately reservation details were extracted from the transcript text. It was examined whether the model successfully identified the date, time, and number of guests within the transcript. This model extracted date information with 90% accuracy, time information with 90% accuracy, and guest count with 96% accuracy. The information extraction time was approximately 0.95 seconds.

Analysis revealed a 5 percentage point decrease in accuracy (to 85%) when the Gemini-2.0-Flash and Gemini-2.5-Flash-Preview-05-20 models converted date information within the text to the day, month, year format. For these intent extraction models, only date accuracy was evaluated. This is because at this stage, the model's success in accurately converting natural language date expressions into calendar data is of paramount importance. This decrease can be attributed to the varied interpretation of ambiguous expressions such as next week or next month in the test samples.

To measure the system's overall task success rate and completion time, a mobile application was presented to 20 participants, each performing trials for three different scenarios (varying dates, times, and guest counts). The average completion time and accuracy of these trials are presented in Table 1.

Table 2 System evaluation table.

Metric	Average
Task success rate	%94
Completion time	8.4s

According to Table 2, the system's overall task success rate was determined to be 94%. This indicates that the system is largely capable of accurately processing users' voice-based reservation requests. The average completion time for a reservation transaction was measured at 8.4 seconds. This duration signifies a substantial time saving compared to reservations made via manual form filling or through call centers. The Whisper and Gemini combination, chosen as the default solution, demonstrated its potential for improving operational efficiency and user experience with a total processing time of approximately 5 seconds.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This study introduced a voice-based restaurant reservation system designed to transform reservation processes within the hotel and restaurant sectors. The developed system integrates Protel A.Ş.'s Turyid Loyalty mobile application with the Check and Place table-management platform, thereby simplifying the user experience and enhancing operational efficiency. By combining Speech-to-Text and Natural Language Processing technologies, the system can automatically extract essential reservation details, such as date, time, and guest count, from user voice requests with high accuracy.

The research findings demonstrated the practical applicability of the proposed voice-based reservation system by meeting both accuracy and speed criteria for task completion, achieving a 94% task success rate and an average completion time of 8.4 seconds with real-world data. These results clearly indicate the system's potential for improving operational efficiency and enhancing the user experience.

The developed microservice architecture offers a scalable, maintainable, and easily integrable structure with existing hotel-restaurant infrastructures. The system provides robust speech-to-intent conversion even in noisy real-world conditions, ensuring a multichannel and consistent reservation experience. Its ability to automatically retrieve user data and combine it with reservation details delivers a personalized and frictionless experience, simultaneously boosting both customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. This work has contributed a comprehensive architecture to the literature by integrating fragmented approaches in voice-based reservations, thereby automating the speech-to-text-to-intent-to-calendar chain from start to finish.

Future iterations of the system will incorporate a verification loop to enhance data integrity. After a voice command is processed, the transcribed text and extracted reservation details will be shown to the user—both visually within the app and audibly via Text-to-Speech (TTS). A multi-modal confirmation mechanism, allowing for either explicit voice approval (e.g., semantic confirmation commands) or direct UI interaction will be implemented to ensure accuracy before finalization. Furthermore, the system will include a feedback workflow that allows users to correct specific parameters or re-initiate the recording process in case of discrepancies, thereby establishing a fully interactive and error-resilient user experience.

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